

ADABIY NUTQ USLUBLARI VA ULARNING O'ZBEK TILIDAGI O'RNI**Mavsumova Nilufar Tolibjon qizi**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mazkur maqolada o'zbek tilida mavjud uslublar va uning turlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan bo'libm ularning o'zbek adabiy tilidagi o'rni va xususiyatlari ochib berilgan.

Uslubiyat turlarini yoritib berish uslubiyat o'qitish asosiy vazifalarini belgilash taqozo etadi.

1. Uslubiyatni tilni amaliy-nutqiy jihatdan tadqiq etuvchi fan sifatida o'rganish.
2. Uslubiyatning sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili va adabiyot nazariyasi fanlari doirasidagi o'rni, o'zaro munosabatini ko'rsatish...
3. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili uslubiyatlarini, ularning lisoniy va nolisoniy alomatlarini tasvirlash.
4. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili leksikasi va frazeologiyasining funksional-stilistik va ekspressiv-stilistik qatlamlarini, ularning lingvistik xususiyatlari bilan tanishtirish, fonitika, morfologiya, so'z yasalishi va sintaksisning boyligini tasvirlash va boshqalarini yoritib berish.

Adabiy nutq – xalq tilining ishlov berilgan, qat'iy qoidalashtirilgan ko'rinishi. U ko'p shivali millatning yaxlitligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Har bir soz va qo'shimchani adabiy nutqdagi talafuzi va imlosi, tinish belgilarining qo'llanishi, odatda qoida sifatida qonun bilan aniq belgilab qo'yiladi. Zarur hollarda bu qoidalarga amal qilmaslik qo'pol xato, qonunni buzish sifatida baholanadi. Og'zaki adabiy nutqning ham, yozma adabiy nutqning ham o'z qoidalari bor. Har doim ham aytilganidek yozish, yozilgandek aytish to'g'ri bo'lavermaydi. Odatda, barcha rasmiy yozishmalar, hujjatlar, o'qitish va nashr ishlari, ommaviy axborot vositalarining xabarlari adabiy nutqda beriladi.

Adabiy nutq me'yorlariga amal qilmaslik savodsizlik va madaniyatsizlik emas, balki o'z ona tiliga nisbatan hurmatsizlikdir. "Ona tili" o'quv predmeti o'quvchilarni ana shu adabiy nutq me'yorlari bilan qurollantoradi, ularning so'z boyligini oshirib, so'z qo'llash malakasini shakllantiradi va yuksaltiradi. Faqat rasmiy holatlarda adabiy nutq me'yorlariga rioya qilish

talab etiladi. Esda tutish lozimki, oila davrasida, o'zaro suhbatlarda shiva nutqida so'zlash ayb emas. Madaniyatli kishi adabiy nutqqa ham, sheva nutqiga ham o'z o'rnida rioya qiladi.

Adabiy nutqning turli qo'llanish sohalari mavjud. Masalan, og'zaki so'zlashuv sohasi, badiiy adabiyot sohasi, axborot-targ'ibot sohasi, ish uyritish sohasi, ilmiy soha.

Adabiy nutqning biror sohaga hoslangan bunday ko'rinishi adabiy nutq uslubi deyiladi.

So'zlashuv uslubi- oilada, ko'cha-ko'yda fikr almashish jarayonida qo'llanadigan nutq uslubi so'zlashuv uslubi ko'pincha dialog shaklida bo'ladi. So'zlashuv uslubida adabiy nutqning og'zaki me'yorlariga qat'iy rioya qilish talab etilmaydi. Ammo turli sheva vakillari suhbatida adabiy nutqning og'zaki me'yorlariga rioya qilish madaniyatlilik hisoblanadi.

So'zlashuv uslubi – bir so'z uslubi, odamlar o'rtasida to'g'ridan to'g'ri muloqot qilish uchun xizmat qiladi. Uning asosiy vazifasi – kommunikativ (axborot almashinuvi).

So'zlashuv uslubi nafaqat taqdim etadi, balkim yozma ravishda ham bo'ladi. So'zlashuv uslubida hamda badiiy uslubda fonetik vositalardan ko'proq foydalaniladi. Fonetik vositalar deganda ba'zi nutq tovushlari, urg'u, ohang va ularning nutqiy ta'sirchanligi tushuniladi. So'zdagi unilarning cho'zib talaffuz qilinishi ajablanish, ta'kid, kuchaytirish, hayajon, olqish, erkalash, yalinish kabi konnotativ ma'nolarni ifodalaydi. Chunonchi, *Qorako'z opaaa, sizga xaaat! Katta konvertda xaaat!!!* (N.Qobul) Undoshlarni ikkilantirish kuchli hayajonni, qo'rquv yoki nutqiy kamchilikni ifodalashga xizmat qiladi. Masalan, *Bbbo'la qoling, ssovqotib ketdim-ku!* (M.Ismoilij)

Badiiy uslub – badiiy adabiyotga xos nutqdir unda badiiylik- ifodaviylik, ta'sirchanlik kuchli bo'ladi.

Publitsistik uslub – rasmiy axborot berishga, davrning ijtimoiy siyosiy masalalarini aks ettirishga mo'ljallangan ommaviy axborot vositalari (Radio-televideneye, gazeta jurnallar) uslubidir.

Ilmiy uslub – ilmiy asarlar, ilmiy jurnallar, darslik va qo'llanmalar yoziladigan uslub, unda ilmiy atamalardan keng foydalaniladi, ko'chma ma'noli til ifodalari nihoyatda kam ishlatiladi.

Rasmiy-idoraviy uslub – davlat qonunlari, Prezident farmonlari, hukumat qarorlari, turli hujjatlar, ish qog'ozlari, idoralararo yozishmalar yoziladigan uslub. Rasmiy-idoraviy uslubda gaplar ixcham va aniq, mazmunli qudratli, ko'pincha, egasiz, kesimlari majhul nisbatda bo'ladi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og’ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>
2. Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.
3. Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.
4. Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.
5. Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.
6. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.
7. Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.
8. Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

9. Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.
10. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.
11. Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.
12. Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.
13. Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY “A FRIEND IN NEED” BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 240–244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>
14. Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE’S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.
15. Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.
16. Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.
17. Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.
18. Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>
19. Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

20. Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Ҳамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.
21. Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.
22. NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).
23. Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.